

IMPROVEMENT OF THE QUALITY MANAGEMENT MECHANISMS OF GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS

Research Institute of Pedagogical Sciences of Uzbekistan

named after T.N. Kori Niyoz

3rd stage foundation doctoral student

Ibragimova Gulnoza Sayidmurodovna

ANNOTATION: The article explores the topic improvement of the quality management mechanisms of general secondary schools. Moreover, effective ways of developing the quality in education and main key activities which implementation involves were highlighted by author. Additionally, the article covers recent reforms which were hold in education of Uzbekistan.

KEY WORDS: *Quality, policy makers, suspicion, manufacturing, strategic planning, secondary schools, self-management, adjustments.*

Today's rapidly developing age requires innovative approaches, new perspectives and modern approaches in every aspect of our lives. It is necessary for every professional who aims for high goals to have such qualities and to develop intensively typical of the times. In particular, education is the most important area that determines the state's present and future. Education is a great force capable of radically changing a person's life, and if this force is not continuously controlled, its negative effects can bring down the whole country. In this place, the first knowledge that will be given at school is of great importance in what kind of profession the child will have in the future, and will become a useful representative of the society. For this reason, today, improving the quality of education is the most important goal, and many reforms at the state level are directed to this area. The fact that our president called 2023 "the year of human attention and quality education" is proof of our above opinion. In order to attract today's young learners, lessons should include various interactive methods,

interesting principles and, of course, modern technologies. Already, the lessons conducted on the basis of interactive methods, regardless of the subject, are organized in a high-quality, understandable and certainly interesting way.

Quality education is a great concern in many societies across the world. In a highly competitive education sector, the success of academic institutions depends on the quality of education. Educationalists, policy makers, scholars, and researchers are showing their sincere interest towards the total quality management (TQM) as it is recognized as an effective management philosophy for continuous improvement, customer satisfaction, and organizational excellence. Since this concept was initially developed in the manufacturing sector, therefore, there is a great deal of suspicion whether this philosophy is applicable in education. According to Koslowski, in this age of intense competition, quality education is a major concern [1]. The pressure and demand for quality education are increasing. All concerned parties of the education are actively considering implementing TQM in education because it is believed that quality education is one of the fundamental building blocks of economic development. Regarding the applicability of TQM in education, there is a serious debate since this concept was initially developed for manufacturing organizations. It is essential to resolve this problem. While conducting an initial investigation it was also revealed that there are critical challenges in implementing TQM in education. It is also imperative to explore the nature of those challenges so that academic institutions can take proper measure proactively while pursuing TQM in education[2].

One management tool that has been acclaimed internationally as effective in improving the performance of state owned enterprises as well as government departments is the use of strategic planning. Strategic planning is important to any organizational work performance because it determines the organization's success or failure. According to Bryson a strategy is a plan that is intended to achieve a particular purpose. It is a disciplined effort to produce fundamental decisions and actions that shape and guide what an organization is, what it does and how it does

it with a focus on the future. These days there is an increasing need for effective and efficient development of strategic plan for secondary schools. Many organizations around the globe have also started taking interest in developing strategic plans because many policies and programmes which they initiated at different times have failed them. Introducing strategies and plans have been to acquire quality education and improve standard and bring the school to effective self-management[4]. A school's strategic plan is the physical document that embodies the guiding orientation regarding how to manage the school within a larger national and local development perspective. Such a plan can lead to school effectiveness, improvement and development when properly implemented. According to Chang (2008) a strategic plan is a living document that includes policy direction, implementation strategies, actions and benchmarks for implementation, monitoring and evaluation, as well as the expenditure framework which allows + in areas for developments during implementation. This plan entails the school's analysis of its strategic issues for development, prioritization, planning to address such issues and, finally, implementing a plan to address these identified issues for development. It ensures that the learners receive quality education in terms of holistic development and academic achievement. This explains that School Developed Strategic Plan is a live document which automatically links to the whole school self-evaluation reports and Performance Appraisal Objectives where relevant. In this regard some governments therefore made it mandatory for institutions to develop strategic plans in line with the national strategic plan. It becomes a requirement that public organizations including educational institution have to develop strategic plans as a means of enhancing results based management and efficiency in their operations. The plans provide direction in regard to resource targeting and programme implementation.

Education systems must have a powerful and coherent educational improvement strategy in order to improve student academic achievement[3]. The strategic management of human capital and the education system's educational

improvement strategy are inextricably linked. According to Pearce & Robinson (2013) implementation involves three key activities; (1) developing short term objectives which are implementable, (2) developing functional tactics, and (3) developing policies that empower action. Aldehyyat, Al Khattab, and Anchor (2011) pointed out that a school that formulates and implements strategic plan derives benefits such as having negotiated and agreed clear goals and objectives, communication of the set goals to various stake holders, providing a base upon which progress can be measured, building strong and functional teams in management staff who have clear vision on how the school will be in future, providing the school management with new ideas which can steer the school to greater heights of excellence and commits the school funds to a well-organized and coherent development agenda.

Huge changes are taking place in all aspects of life in Uzbekistan, including the education system. Taking into account that the main strength of powerful countries is their mature and well-rounded young people, today the education sector in our country, especially schools Many reforms are being carried out in the education system. This period is widely known as "the period of modernization of Uzbekistan". General secondary education in Uzbekistan is free (implying no tuition fees) and compulsory in the country, and this has resulted in a near-universal enrollments in the sub-sector. While the overall gross enrollment ratio (GER) in grades 1-9 was around 97% in 2016-17, for primary grades (grades 1-4), this was 100% and for secondary education levels (grades 5-9), it was 94%. There are variations across regions regarding the GER, with around 108-111% GER in Tashkent city while only 86% in Karakalpakstan.

Many many decrees which were covered education have been signed by our President[5]. For instance, The decree of the President of Uzbekistan "On approval of the development concept of the public education system by 2030"

was signed. According to the decree, in order to define priorities of systemic reforming of general secondary and extracurricular education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, raise the spiritual-moral and intellectual development of the younger generation to a qualitatively new level, introduce innovative forms and methods of education in the educational process, the Concept of development of the public education system by 2030 has been approved. The decree of the President of Uzbekistan “On approval of the development concept of the public education system by 2030” was signed. According to the decree, in order to define priorities of systemic reforming of general secondary and extracurricular education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, raise the spiritual-moral and intellectual development of the younger generation to a qualitatively new level, introduce innovative forms and methods of education in the educational process, the Concept of development of the public education system by 2030 has been approved.

To sum up, we should highlighted that Education is something that’s not only needed on a personal level, but also on a global level, as it’s something that keeps our world safe and makes it a more peaceful place. Education tends to teach people the difference between right and wrong, and can help people stay out of risky situations. In today’s society, having an education is considered a vital part of being accepted by those around you. Having an education is believed to make you a useful part of society, and can make you feel like a contributing member as well. An educated society is crucial for economic growth. We need people to continue to learn and research in order to constantly stay innovative. [Countries with higher literacy rates](#) also tend to be in better economic situations. With a more educated population, more employment opportunities are opened.

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